

Direct Nose-to-brain drug delivery: Challenges and progress approaching brain targeting in the treatment of neurological disorders

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Abstract:

Nose-to-brain drug delivery to the treatment of various central nervous system (CNS) disorder has been challenging, despite the rapid development of many novel treatment approaches. The blood–brain barrier (BBB) is one of the major consequences in the treatment of CNS disorder, having significant role in the protection of the brain but concurrently initiate the main limiting barrier for drugs targeting the brain. Nasal drug delivery has attained significant interest for brain targeting over the past decades, the drug is directly delivered to the brain by the trigeminal and olfactory pathway. Due to the high permeability, high vasculature, low enzymatic environment of nasal cavity and avoidance of hepatic first pass metabolism are excellent suitable for systemic delivery of drug molecule through nasal route. Several drug delivery devices for nasal application of liquid, semisolid and solid formulation are investigated to deliver the drugs to the treat most emergency CNS disorder (Epilepsy, Parkinson's disorder, Alzheimer's disorders and other neurological disorders) because it requires rapid or specific targeted drug delivery to the brain. This review sets are discussing some factors affecting nasal absorption, barriers to nasal absorption, strategies to improve nasal absorption, new design & developments in nasal formulation and applications of nasal drug delivery system and nasal delivery device.

Introduction

Nose to brain drug delivery is a targeted approach to deliver a drug directly in the brain through the nasal route. Intranasal drug delivery has been recognized as an excellent route of therapeutic compounds because it avoids First-Pass Metabolism and achieves a higher concentration of drugs in the central nervous system (CNS) at a low dose. Nasal mucosa is studied as a potential administration route to achieve rapid onset of action and higher level of drug absorption (Mittal et al., 2013). Nasal cavity having a larger surface area, porous endothelial membrane, high total blood flow and avoidance of problem of first-pass metabolism are these few reasons. Researcher are interested in nasal route for the systemic delivery of therapeutic components due to their high degree of permeability of nasal mucosa (Ugwoke et al., 2005).

Intranasal drug delivery to the brain is major challenge due to presence of two physiological barrier that reduce the delivery of drug to the central nervous system (CNS), Blood brain barrier (BBB) and Blood cerebrospinal fluid barrier (BCSFB). For many years drugs have been administrated into nasal route for both topical and systemic action. Topical administration for the treatment of local disorders like nasal allergy, nasal infections and nasal congestion (Garcia et al., 2005). Nose to brain drug delivery approach is a greater area of target for direct transport pathway of drug through olfactory and trigeminal nerve cells through nose they can bypassing the BBB and directly enter into the brain. Olfactory region of the nasal mucosa is directly connection between nose and brain is explored for CNS acting drugs. Drug or Prodrug is absorbed through active and passive transport to cross the tight

junction of the BBB. Drug molecules in applied to nasal mucosa is directly reaches to the brain either by direct transport from olfactory region to the brain and from blood to brain or CSF (Tellingan et al.,2015).

The olfactory region, next to the respiratory region in which drug is directly absorbed into the brain by different mechanism like as Transcellular, Paracellular, Olfactory and Trigeminal neural pathways. In recent years, most of therapeutic compound and proteins and peptides is delivered efficiently by using nose to brain delivery. This strategy is very useful to treat various CNS disorder including, Brain tumours, Parkinson disorder, Multiple sclerosis, Alzheimer disorder, Epilepsy and Psychiatric disorder (Fernandes et al.,2010; Swartling et al.,2016).

Advantages

1. Rapid drug absorption and quick onset of action can be achieved.
2. It avoids hepatic First-Pass Metabolism.
3. It avoids drug degradation in Gastrointestinal tract.
4. Some drugs that are orally not absorbed can be achieved to the systemic circulation by the nasal route.
5. The Bioavailability of larger molecules can be improved by using absorption enhancers or other approaches.
6. Better patient compliance and self-medication, especially for those on long term therapy, when compared with parenteral formulation.
7. Low molecular weight of some therapeutic compounds it can shows excellent bioavailability.
8. It is rapid, Safe, non-invasive and convenient method of drug delivery by nasal route.

Limitation

1. Absorption enhancer may create mucosal toxicity used in nasal formulation.
2. Nasal cavity gives smaller absorption surface area as compared to gastrointestinal tract.
3. Rapid elimination of drug molecules from nasal cavity due to mucociliary clearance.
4. It difficult to patients when compared to oral delivery system since there is a possibility of nasal irritation.
5. There is a risk of nasal side effects and irreversible damage of the cilia on the nasal mucosa especially material and other ingredients added to the formulation.
6. Some surfactants are used as chemical enhancers in nasal formulations it may disturb and alike dissolve membrane in high concentration.

Anatomy and Physiology of Nasal Cavity

To study nasal drug absorption and pathways, Drug molecules need to penetrate before reaching the brain, it is crucial to get know its function and anatomical and cellular structure of the nasal cavity. The nose is responsible for multiple physiological function such as olfaction and inhaled air. The nasal cavity is divided into two halves by the nasal septum and extends posterior to the midsagittal plane (Crowe et al., 2018). The cavities are lined with a layer of mucosa, and the total surface area of both nasal cavities 150-160cm² (Lochhead and Thorne et al., 2012; Mygind and Anggard et al., 1984; Mygind and Dahi et al., 1998).

The nasal cavity consists three main regions are nasal vestibule, olfactory region and respiratory region. The first is the nasal vestibule region, it is most anterior and located immediately at the nostril openings. This region surface area is around 0.6cm² and it contain number of nasal hairs which serve to filter inhaled particles. The primary cell type in this nasal vestibule area which is covered with ciliated cells like squamous epithelial cells. Due to the surface area and cellular structure the absorption of drugs is very limited in this nasal

vestibule region. The respiratory region which is covered with lateral walls of the nasal cavities, including the three major projecting turbinates (Lower, middle and upper nasal turbinates). This respiratory region has the largest surface area at 130cm² available for drug absorption and it is also the most vascular region (Watelet and Van Cauwenberge et al., 1998). There are four major cell types: Goblet, ciliated, non-ciliated columnar and basal cells. Goblet cells secrete mucin to create the mucus membrane together with some of the nasal glands, which is turned over at varying rates (Merkus et al., 1998). Depending on the natural environment such as temperature and Humidity. The mucus secretion is composed of about 95% water, 2% mucin, 1% salts, 1% lipids and 1% proteins like as albumin, lysozyme, immunoglobulins and lactoferrin (Kaliner M et al., 1984). This mucus secretion gives immune protection against inhaled micro-organisms such as bacteria and viruses.

Figure 1: Anatomy of nose and nasal epithelium

It performs a various physiological function.

- It covers the mucosa membrane and physically and enzymatically protection.
- The mucus has water-holding capacity.
- It exhibits surface electrical activity.
- It allows efficient heat transfer.
- It acts as adhesive and transports particulate material towards the nasopharynx (Bernstein JM et al., 1997).

The mucociliary clearance is approximately 20min but it subject to great inter subject variability. The mucociliary clearance is dependent on the function of cilia and the characteristics of the covering mucus which can be influenced by acute and chronic disorders like a respiratory tract infection (Jadhav et al., 2007; Soeda et al., 2008). Many substances are influences the Mucociliary clearance of the airways, either by inhibition or stimulation. A stimulatory effect of drugs on the Mucociliary clearance is a clinical importance, because these substances can possibly use to improve pathological conditions of mucociliary clearance. Composition (Drug and other ingredients) of intranasal formulation with a too be pronounced mucociliary clearance impairing activity may limit their use (Ugwoke et al., 2005; Basu et al., 2010).

Mechanism of drug absorption across Nasal Mucosa

The absorption of drug molecules from the nasal cavity must pass through the mucus layers. Drug molecules across nasal mucosa under two mechanisms.

- Paracellular (extracellular) mechanism.
- Transcellular (intracellular) mechanism.

Paracellular (extracellular) mechanism

The first paracellular mechanism is passive and slow aqueous route of transport through intracellular tight junctions or open clefts of the epithelial cells of the nasal mucosa. In nose to brain transport of drug, the paracellular transport involves two extracellular routes, first across the olfactory neurons and the second across the trigeminal nerve. After reaching the olfactory bulb or trigeminal region the drug molecules are entered other brain regions by simple diffusion, facilitated diffusion by arterial pulsation driven perivascular pump.

Paracellular mechanism is concluded inverse log-log correlation between nasal absorption and molecular weight of hydrophilic compounds. Low bioavailability is observed for drugs having molecular weight greater than 1000 Daltons irrespective of their lipophilicity. Molecules like chitosan is tried to manipulate the junctions between the nasal epithelium cells to facilitate trans nasal absorption (Bahadur et al., 2012; Prajapati et al., 2012).

Figure 2: Mechanism of nasal drug absorption

Transcellular (intracellular) mechanism

The second transcellular mechanism entails transport through a lipoidal route by either by receptor mediated endocytosis (passive diffusion, fluid phase endocytosis). This transcellular Mechanism for the trans nasal absorption of both small and large lipophilic molecules. Transcellular drug uptake is mainly a function of lipophilic nature of drug molecules with highly lipophilic drugs being expected to have rapid trans nasal uptake. This transcellular mechanism is a slow process for taking hours for nasally administered drugs to reach the olfactory bulb through intracellular axonal transport by processes like endocytosis within the olfactory neurons (Kublik et al., 1998; Nagpal et al., 2013).

Drug Transport Pathways of Nose to the Brain Delivery

Neural pathways

The neural pathways are involved olfactory and trigeminal neural Pathways which provide connection between the nasal mucosa and the brain; it is excellent pathway for the nose to brain delivery of drugs and therapeutics.

Olfactory neural pathways

Olfactory neural pathways is major pathway for the nose to brain drug delivery. Drug molecules is travelled from the olfactory region in the nasal cavity to CSF or brain parenchyma, it is also transverse to the nasal olfactory epithelium. This Olfactory pathway, the arachnoid membrane enclosing the subarachnoid space having three different major pathways across the olfactory epithelium

First is a transcellular pathway specially across the Sustentacular cells act receptor mediated endocytosis, fluid phase endocytosis or the passive diffusion for the lipophilic drugs is mediated rapidly and at a high rate. This Olfactory neural route is major responsible for the transport of lipophilic drug molecules and the transport rate is mainly depended in their lipophilicity.

Second is a paracellular pathway in which, the tight junctions between Sustentacular cells having the clefts between olfactory neurons and Sustentacular cells. Intranasal absorption of hydrophilic especially across the Sustentacular cells act receptor mediated endocytosis, fluid phase endocytosis or the passive diffusion for the lipophilic drugs is mediated rapidly and at a high rate. This route is mainly responsible for the transport of lipophilic drug molecules and the transport rate is mainly depended in their lipophilicity (Misra et al., 2012). The molecular weight of drugs up to 6000 Dalton with absorption enhancers (Kumar et al., 2008). Drugs have diffusion mechanism through aqueous channels or pores. This pathway is slow and it is responsible for the transport of hydrophilic drugs under rate dependency on the molecular mass of the drug material. Pharmaceutical drugs with a molecular weight in the range between 300 - 1000 Dalton shows excellent bioavailability without absorption enhancer.

Third is olfactory nerve pathway in which, the drug is taken up to the neuronal cells by endocytosis or pinocytosis mechanism and transported by the intracellular axonal transport to the olfactory bulb. The different modes of drug transport across the nasal olfactory epithelium are the transcellular passive diffusion, Paracellular passive diffusion, efflux transport, transcytosis transports and the olfactory region of brain.

Trigeminal neural pathways

Trigeminal nerve pathways are largest nerve pathway with all cranial nerve pathways in which, innervates the respiratory and olfactory epithelium of the nasal passages and to enters the central nervous system (CNS). The small portion of the trigeminal nerve pathways terminates the olfactory bulbs. The trigeminal nerve communicates in sensory information from the nasal cavity, oral cavity, eyelids and the cornea to CNS through ophthalmic, maxillary and the mandibular divisions of trigeminal nerves. The former two is sensory functions while later the both sensory and motor functions (Nagpal et al., 2013). The ophthalmic and maxillary nerve is most important for nose to brain delivery as neurons from these branches passed directly through the nasal mucosa.

The excellent feature of the trigeminal nerve is that enters into the brain from the respiratory epithelium of the nasal passages at the two sites first through anterior lacerated foramen near the pons and second through cribriform plate near olfactory bulb is producing the entry points into the both caudal and rostral brain areas following the nose to brain administrations. Since the portion of the trigeminal nerve pathway enters the brain through the cribriform plate onward the olfactory pathway, It is challenging to differentiate the nose to brain administered drugs reach the olfactory bulbs and other rostral brain areas (anterior olfactory nucleus and frontal cortex) through olfactory pathway, brainstem, spinal cord via trigeminal pathway and the both extracellular, intracellular pathways is involved for bypassing the BBB (Thorne et al., 2004; Garcia et al., 2005; Tellingan et al., 2015).

Vascular pathway

Pharmaceutical drugs or Therapeutic agents is transported in nose to brain through the blood vessels supplying the nasal cavity to systemic circulation following the intranasal administration. Nasal route is use to deliver drug to the systemic circulation through absorption into the capillary blood vessels underlying the nasal mucosa. The nasal mucosa is highly vascularised for receiving blood supply from branches of both the internal and external carotid artery, including the branches of the facial artery and maxillary artery. The olfactory mucosa was received blood from the anterior and posterior ethmoidal artery (smallest artery of ocular cavity), where the respiratory mucosa is received the blood from the sphenopalatine artery (Branches of the maxillary artery). The relative density of the blood vessels is higher in the respiratory mucosa than the olfactory mucosa, making the former an ideal region for adsorption of drug into the systemic circulation. (Schaefer et al., 2002).

The respiratory region is the combination of the continuous and fenestrated endothelium that allowing the egress of both small and large molecules into the blood subsequent transport cross the BBB to the brain. This is especially true for small lipophilic drugs which more easily enter to the blood stream and it can cross the BBB compared to large hydrophilic molecules such as proteins and peptides or high molecular weight compounds. The therapeutics is distributed throughout the systemic circulation and it enter in the blood supply to the nasal passages to be rapidly transferred to that carotid arterial blood supply to the brain and spinal cord, this process known as counter-current transfer.(Schaefer et al., 2002).

The drug molecules are entered to the brain through the perivascular spaces in the nasal passages or after reaching the brain parenchyma to be distributed throughout the brain. The perivascular spaces are act as a lymphatic system for the brain, where the neuron derived substance. is cleared from brain interstitial fluid by entering perivascular channels associated with cerebral blood vessel. The vascular pathway is involving perivascular channels associated with blood vessel as a potential for nose to brain drug transport mechanism. Perivascular transport is a bulk flow mechanism rather than the diffusing alone the arterial pulsations were driving forces for the perivascular transports. The high level of drug in the walls of cerebral blood vessels and carotid arteries, even after removal of blood by saline perfusion, that proposed to nose to brain delivery of the drugs gain access to the perivascular spaces (Basu et al., 2010).

Cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) pathway

The CSF pathway is connected to the subarachnoid space containing CSF, perineural spaces enveloping olfactory nerves and the nasal lymphatics. The CSF circulation and drainage provide access for nose to brain administered drugs to the CSF and other areas of the brain. The CSF was produced by secretion at the four choroid Plexi, especially at the fourth and lateral ventricles. CSF is a secretory fluid produced by the choroid plexi to cushion the brain. The tracers are injected into the CSF in the cerebral ventricles or subarachnoid space drain to the underside of the olfactory bulbs into channels associated with olfactory nerves traversing the cribriform plate that reach the nasal lymphatic system and cervical lymph nodes. Hence CSF flows along the olfactory sub mucosa in the roof of the nasal cavity (Tellingan et al., 2015).

Intranasal administration of drugs is a same pathway from the nasal cavity to CSF into the brain interstitial spaces and perivascular spaces for distribution throughout the brain. In direct nose to brain administration is concluded by the drugs gains direct access to the CSF form the nasal cavity followed by consequent distribution to the brain and spinal cord. The transport is mainly dependent on the lipophilicity, molecular weight and degree of ionization of drug molecules (Dey et al., 2011; Mittal et al., 2013).

Lymphatic pathways

The CSF production through choroid plexus and their absorption through arachnoid villi to the cerebral venous sinuses taken remained extensively accepted. The anatomical and functional connection between the extracranial lymphatics (cervical lymphatics and nasal submucosa) and subarachnoid spaces through the perineural spaces to the cribriform plate. Nasal submucosa is consisting of dense vascular network that leads to systemic circulation and dense network of lymphatics that communicates directly with the subarachnoid spaces (Misra et al., 2012).

The nasal submucosal lymphatics leads directly to the subarachnoid space through a perineural route to the cribriform plate. Nasal lymphatics action a direct transport through the subarachnoid space and have been proposed as a potential pathway for the invasion of the microbes such as *S. pneumoniae*, *N. meningitis* or *H. influenza* responsible for bacterial meningitis (Kumar et al., 2013; Fernandes et al., 2010).

Figure 3: Drug Transport Pathways of Nose to the Brain Delivery

Factors Influencing Nasal Drug Absorption

There obtain various factors that are affect the permeation of drugs is administered through nasal route. The factor affecting nasal absorption of drugs, The Physicochemical, formulation and biological factor.

Biological factors which affect nasal drug absorption

Nasal blood flow

Nasal mucosa is supplied by high vasculature and presents a large surface area making an excellent drug absorption. The blood flow is consequence significantly the systemic nasal absorption of drugs that enhanced the drug is passing through the membrane reaching to the regular circulation. Drug absorption is taken placed by the diffusion, the excellent blood flow is necessary to maintain the concentration gradient from the site of absorption to blood. The vasodilation and vasoconstriction can determine the blood flow and the rate extent of drug to be absorbed (Soni et al., 2004). The blood vessels in the nasal mucosa are surrounded by adrenergic nerves which act as alpha adrenoreceptor stimulation of these receptors is shows to decreases blood flow and blood content in the nose of the humans and animals.

The nasal blood flow is affected by the external and physiological factors such as ambient temperature, humidity, vasoactive drugs, trauma and inflammation. The psychological factors such as emotion, fear, anxiety and frustration. The Nasal flow was sensitive to different locally or systemically acting drugs, such as oxymetazoline and clonidine decreases the blood flow of histamines, albuterol, isoproterenol, Phenylephrine and fenoterolare is shown to increases the blood flow, this effect is important in determining the nasal drug absorption due to their effect on blood flow (Ugwoke et al., 2005; Mittal et al., 2013).

Enzymatic activity

Nasal administration of drugs to prevent gastrointestinal and hepatic first pass the drug is significantly metabolized in lumen of nasal cavity and the passage across the nasal epithelial barrier due to the presence of cytochrome P450 dependant Monooxygenase, lactose dehydrogenase, oxidoreductase, hydrolase, acid phosphatase and esterase (Soni et al., 2004). The cytochrome P450 isoenzyme metabolized the drug such as cocaine, nicotine, alcohols, progesterone and decongestants. The proteolytic enzymes (aminopeptidases and protease) were found they are believed to be the primary barrier against the absorption of protein and peptide drugs such as, calcitonin, insulin and Desmopressin. This various enzyme is existed in the nasal mucosa may affect the pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamics profile of nasally administered drugs (Jain *et al.*, 2010).

Mucociliary clearance

Mucociliary clearance is most important function to elimination of foreign substances and particles from the nasal cavity consequently preventing them from reaching the lower airways. Intranasal administration of drugs is cleared from the nasal cavity with a half-life of clearance about 15 min. with the result of limiting time available for absorption (Hussain *et al.*, 1998). The naturally mucociliary passage time of humans 12-15 min. having a rapid mucociliary clearance of drug formulations that are deposited in the nasal mucosa. It is almost important factor hidden the low bioavailability of nose to brain administration of drugs. Most of drug molecules having hormonal changes in the body, formulation factors and pathological conditions especially rheology to affect mucociliary clearance and turn to utilize significant consequence on drug permeability (Prajapati et al., 2012).

Physical condition of the nasal mucosa

The physical condition of nasal mucosa is important consequence on the drug absorption. There hold times when the mucosa is crushing, blending or dry. The infection may be suffering from rhinorrhoea, sinusitis and nasal local infection. In person suffering from several nasal allergies as an excessive nasal secretion elsewhere the formulation before the drug is chance to getting absorbed through the mucosa before acting locally.

Physiochemical Factors Influencing Nasal Drug Absorption

Molecular Weight

The compound having a molecular weight less than < 300 Dalton in solution are rapidly and effectively absorbed across the nasal membrane in aqueous channels having a 100% bioavailability. Molecular weight of lipophilic drugs is greater than 1000 Dalton, the nasal absorption is decreased. The pharmaceutical or therapeutic agent molecular weight 1000-6000 Dalton achieve excellent bioavailability with the help of absorption enhancers (Misra et al., 2012).

Lipophilicity

Lipophilicity is a major physicochemical factor that restriction the transport of therapeutics on nasal administration. On increasing lipophilicity of the therapeutic compounds, the

permeation of the compounds normally increases through nasal mucosa. The lipid domain plays an important role in the barrier function of these membranes (Jain et al., 2010).

Dissociation constant

The Nasal drug absorption mainly depends on the dissociation constant (pKa) of the drug molecules and on the pH of the nasal absorption site (5.0-6.5). pKa is depends in degree of ionization and degree of non-ionization. The nasal absorption of weak electrolytes depends on the degree of ionization and the highest absorption occurs for the no ionized species (Dhuria et al., 2010).

Partition coefficient

The nasal membrane is essentially lipophilic so, the drug absorption is decline with decreases in lipophilicity. Thus, the polar drug is not easily transported across nasal mucosa. The lipophilicity is too high, the drug does not dissolve in the aqueous environment of nasal cavity. In natural, the passage across bio membranes is affected not only by lipophilicity/hydrophilicity but also by the amount of drug existing as uncharged categories, it was observed that absorption rate increases linearly with increase in partition coefficient (Schaefer et al., 2002).

Solubility

Solubility of drug molecules is a major factor for determining the rate and duration in absorption of drug in nasal physiological pH. The relationship between the drug solubility and its absorption via the nasal route. As nasal secretion is waterier in nature, a drug having an appropriate water solubility for increased dissolution rate. The numerous approaches that may increase solubility of poorly soluble drugs for intranasal administration, co-solvency, Prodrug, and Complexation (cyclodextrins Complexation) salt forms (Lalani et al., 2014).

Polymorphism

Polymorphism is altering the dissolution rate and solubility of drug molecule and so their absorption through biological membranes. It is important to study polymorphic stability and purity of drugs for nasal formulations especially powders and suspensions form (Hussain, 1998).

Formulation factors for Nasal Drug Absorption

pH and mucosal irritancy

The pH of the drug formulation and nasal surface is altering the drug permeation; to avoid nasal irritation, the pH of the nasal formulation should be modified to 4.5-6.5 because lysozyme bacteria are found in nasal secretion, which is major responsible for destroying lysozyme at acidic pH. In addition to avoiding irritation, its outcomes in obtaining efficient drug permeation and prevents the growth of bacteria (Telling et al., 2015).

Osmolarity

The osmolarity of nasal formulations, between 285 and 310 mOsmol/l for nasal drug delivery to avoid the nasal mucosal irritations, specifically the tonic effects. The isotonic solutions

with osmolarity of 308 mOsmol/l were approved for safe and effective (Kulkarni et al., 2013).

Viscosity

The viscosity of the nasal formulation designed for nasal drug delivery ensured the proper contact time between the drug formulation and nasal mucosa. The viscosity increases, increases the contact time and increases the time of permeation. The viscosity of nasal formulation not too high its optimum because it can prevent the normal functions such as ciliary beating or mucociliary clearance and it change the permeability of drug molecule. Thus, viscosity of formulation is maximum, higher the residence time that will affect the total absorption of drug and enhance the bioavailability (Alagusundaram et al., 2010).

Concentration

The concentration gradients play very important role in the nasal drug absorption and permeation process of drug molecule through the nasal membrane due to nasal mucosal damage (Satish BB et al., 2008)

Formulation Strategies for Nose to Brain Drug Delivery System

The Nasal route is efficient for CNS and systemic delivery of various range of drugs, shows low bioavailability alike when administered by this route. The low bioavailability may be due to the low solubility of drugs, rapid enzymatic degradation in nasal cavity, poor membrane permeability and rapid mucociliary clearance. Several strategies are employed to overcome these limitations include, Prodrug approach, enzymatic inhibitor, structural modifications, absorption enhancers and mucoadhesive drug delivery system.

Enzymatic inhibitors

Nasal mucus layer and nasal mucosa is acting as enzymatic barriers for nasal drug delivery system (they have a wide variety of enzymes). Various approaches were used to prevent the enzymatic degradation, involving the use of protease and peptidases inhibitors. Bestatin and comostate amylose were used as aminopeptidases inhibitor and leupeptine, Aprotinin as tyrosine inhibitors is possibly involved in the degradation of calcitonin. The bacitracin, amastatin, boroleucin and puromycin is used to avoid the enzymatic degradations of drugs such as leucine, encephalin and human growth hormone. Finally enzymatic inhibition can be achieved by using certain absorption enhancers such as bile salts and fusidic acid. Disodium ethylene diamine-tetra acetic acid, an absorption enhancer that reduces enzymatic degradation of beta sheet peptide, used for the treatment of Alzheimer's disease (Bahadur et al., 2012; Swartling, 2016).

Absorption enhancer

Absorption enhancer, in which the poor permeability of hydrophilic drugs may be conquered by the used of absorption enhancers that induces reversible modification of epithelial barrier. The absorption enhancer is frequently used in nasal delivery were surfactant (SLS, Poloxamer, tweens, spans), bile salts (sodium glycodeoxycholate, sodium taurodeoxycholate), fatty acids (taurodihydrofusidate, oleic acid, ethyl oleate), Chelators (EDTA, citric acid), peppermint oil and polymers. Some other examples of various polymers such as

cyclodextrines and methylated cyclodextrines, chitosan and trimethyl chitosan, carbopol, starch and animated gelatine. This is major responsible to changes the permeability of epithelial layers of nasal mucosa by modifying phospholipids bilayer and also changes fluidity or reversible openings of tight junctions between epithelial cells and increases paracellular transport of drug molecule (Kulkarni et al., 2013).

The high molecule weight polymeric absorption enhancers were not absorbed and decreased the systemic toxicity in comparison with low molecular weight. Chitosan can interact with protein kinase C and its open tight junctions between epithelial cells to enhance the paracellular transport of polar drugs, its strongly interact with the nasal mucous layer and increases the contact time to overcome mucociliary clearance, thus it can widely use in intranasal dosage forms (Soni et al., 2004). Cyclodextrines complexes interact with the lipophilic components of natural biological membrane and increase the permeability of drugs to increase the absorption. Although cyclodextrines are widely used for nasal delivery, some local and systemic toxicity was reported. The advanced novel formulations such as mucoadhesive, micro and nanoemulsion, microspheres and nanoparticles containing absorption enhancers are demonstrated to better for bypassing the BBB (Nagpal et al., 2013).

Structural Modification

Modification of structure of drug molecule without any altering pharmacological activity, it is one of the major important factors to enhance the nasal drug absorption. The modification of drug molecule, the physicochemical characteristics that are commonly modified, such as the molecular weight, molecular size, partition coefficient and solubility, all favourable for nasal drug absorption. Examples of chemical modification of salmon calcitonin into ecatonin (C-N bond replaced by an S-S bond) was help to improved bioavailability when compared with parent drug molecule (Wong et al., 2012; Fernandes et al., 2010).

Prodrug approach

Prodrug approach, the drugs that administered in the form of solution undergo dissolution previous to absorption. The lipophilic drugs gain easily absorbed through nasal membrane; however, they are poorly water-soluble drugs. So, the approach may be used to get of greater hydrophilic character that can made as aqueous formulation of hydrophobic drugs. when the nasal formulation reaches to systemic circulation, Prodrug must be converted to the parent drug molecule. L-dopa is a poorly water-soluble drug, but when administered as Prodrug its solubility is increases significantly in Comparison with parent drug molecules. Related results were obtained with testosterone, which is a poor water-soluble drug but in the Prodrug form with higher lipophilic nature, Permeation enhance through the membrane. This prodrug approach is applicable to inhibit the enzymatic degradation of drugs in nasal mucosa and to deliver the nasal formulation for maintaining the enzymatic stability. L aspartate--b-ester Prodrug of acyclovir is more permeable and more stable toward enzymatic degradation (it is an example of Prodrug approach). Prodrug approach is an excellent approach for enhancement of bioavailability of large molecular weight compounds such as protein and peptides drugs by this drug delivery (Wu et al., 2008; Nasare et al., 2014).

Co-solvent

This co-solvent approach is used to increase the solubility of the drugs. Frequently used co-solvent includes glycerol, propylene glycol, ethanol, and ethylene glycol, these are nontoxic, non-irritant to nasal mucosa and pharmaceutically acceptable (Bahadur et al., 2012).

Colloidal Carriers in Nose to Brain Drug Delivery Systems

Colloidal drug carriers include microemulsion, nano emulsion, microspheres, nanoparticle, polymeric micelles, liposomes and mucoadhesive solutions its use of colloidal drug carriers for nose to brain drug delivery was to enhance the specifically towards cell or tissue to increase bioavailability of drugs by increasing their diffusion through the biological membranes and protect against enzymatic degradations (Jaiswal et al., 2015).

Nanoparticles

Nanoparticle is a nano-sized particle is size range of 1-1000 nm. It is used to improve the solubility of poorly soluble drugs and permeability of drug molecules (Dingler et al., 1999). This nanoparticulate system is mainly based on biodegradable polymers, have been extensively exploited in targeting drug delivery as they offer excellent improvement in nose to brain delivery by protecting the encapsulated drug from biological and chemical degradation, the extracellular transport by P-gp efflux system increases the CNS availability of drugs. The poly-lactic acid (PLA), poly glycolic acid (PGA), poly-lactide-co-glycolic acid (PLGA), poly-g-caprolactone (PCL), poly-methyl methacrylate, are the polymers known to be biodegradable, biocompatible and non-toxic (Gasco et al., 1997; Ekambaram et al., 2012). Illum et al. demonstrated that chitosan-based nanoparticles can enhance nose-to-brain delivery of drugs compared to equivalent drug solution formulations due to the protection of the drug from degradation and/or efflux back into the nasal cavity. Seju et al., (2011) have reported olanzapine-loaded PLGA nanoparticles for the treatment of psychotic illness, schizophrenia, through nose to brain drug delivery system.

Nanoemulsion

Nanoemulsion is an isotropic mixture of oil, surfactant: cosurfactant (Smix) and drug is known as nanoemulsion. The colloidal size ranges from 50-100 nm are often introduced to as Mini emulsion, nanoemulsion, ultrafine emulsion or the multiple emulsions. These nanoemulsions appear transparent and translucent to the naked eyes and possess stability against sedimentation or creaming. These properties make nanoemulsion as carriers of great interest for fundamental studies and practical utilization in various fields like chemical, cosmetic and pharmaceutical and Biopharmaceutical fields (Bhosale et al., 2014; Jaiswal et al., 2015; Patel et al., 2016).

Microemulsion

Microemulsion is a clear, stable, isotropic mixture of oil, water and surfactant are frequently in the combination with co surfactants this approach is interesting to the pharmaceutical scientist because of their considerable potential to act as drug delivery vehicle by incorporating of extensive range drug molecules. They action the advantages of spontaneous formation, easy manufacturing and scale up, thermodynamic stability and it's important to improve the solubilization and bioavailability. Preparing a pharmaceutically acceptable

dosage from demands a clear perceptive of the microemulsion structure, phase behaviour, factor leading to its thermodynamic stability, factors associated drug release from the formulation and potential uses and limitation of microemulsion system (Lin & Guo et al., 2011).

Polymeric micelles

Polymeric micelles that may serve as nanoscopic drug carriers. Polymeric micelles are the self-assemblies of block of co-polymers and promising nanocarriers for drug and gene delivery, for drug delivery, polymeric micelles have been prepared from biodegradable and biocompatible blocks of copolymers. Polymeric micelles are characterized by core shell structure (Kwon et al., 1996; Nishiyama et al., 2006). It has reported that mixed micelles of bile salts and fatty acid have a synergistic effect on the nasal absorption of peptides.

Liposomes and Proliposomes

Liposomes and Proliposomes is a novel drug delivery system is important to deliver these several routes. Liposomes can be used for targeting and introduction of therapeutic agents to specific site by conjugation or cross linking of targeting moiety to the native liposome or by surface modification of the fabricated liposomal preparations. Positively charged liposomes possessed maximum bioadhesion prolonging the residence time within the nasal cavity thereby improving the bioavailability (Goyal et al., 2005). Free flowing Proliposomes containing propranolol hydrochloride were prepared by Shim et al. and evaluated their potential for trans nasal delivery of propranolol to sustain its plasma concentration. In a study on rats by Wattanathorn et al. intranasal liposomes containing quercetin decreased anxiety like behaviour and enhanced spatial memory. US Patent 6342478 describes a nasal micellar or liposomal preparation for the delivery of fibroblast growth factor to the brain. Vyas et al. have reported multilamellar liposomes for intranasal delivery of nifedipine.

Microspheres

Microspheres involving, mucoadhesive microspheres are the novel systems that are becoming increasingly attractive with nasal drug delivery system. Microspheres can provide prolonged Contact with the nasal mucosa increase the rate and duration of drug absorption. Microspheres or for nasal applications are usually prepared using biocompatible compounds, such as starch, albumin, dextran, hyaluronic acid, chitosan and gelatine, hydroxypropyl methylcellulose, carbopol 934P and several combinations of these polymers. This polymers on absorbing nasal secretions form a gel-like layer which is slowly cleared from the nasal cavity. However, the toxicity of the polymer on the nasal mucosa cells should be critically evaluated. Starch microspheres are most generally used nasal delivery systems and have been successfully tested for insulin, gentamicin, human growth hormone, metoclopramide and Desmopressin. Starch microspheres cause drying of the nasal mucosal surface due to intake of moisture by the microspheres. This conclusion in reversible “shrinkage” of the cells, providing a temporary physical separation of the tight (intercellular) junctions that enhance the absorption of drugs. (Illum et al., 1994).

Nasal Delivery Devices

Nasal drug delivery devices are functional tool for direct nose-brain drug delivery in nasal cavity by using various nasal device.

The nasal devices include

- **Powder formulation devices.**
- **Liquid Formulation devices.**

Liquid formulations presently dominate the nasal drug Market, but nasal powder formulations and devices do exist, and more are in development.

Powder formulation devices

Powder medication formulations are more advantages and it is having a maximum stability than liquid formulations and potential that preservatives may not be required for preparation. It is having a larger dose of drug and they enhance stability of formulation. They can be free from microbes. The nasal powder administration increases the patient compliances. Nasal powder preparation is very useful for the number of proteins, peptides and non-peptide pharmaceutical molecules. Powder-polymer complex formulation allows easy or convenient approach to nasal delivery of drugs.

Dry powder inhaler

Dry powder inhalers are device through which a dry powder formulation of an active drug is delivered for local or systemic effect through the pulmonary route. This dry powder inhalers are bolus drug delivery formulation that contain solid drug, suspended or dissolved in a non-polar volatile propellant or in dry powder inhaler that is fluidized when the patient inhales. These are generally used to treatment of respiratory diseases such as asthma, bronchitis, emphysema and COPD and have also been used in the treatment of diabetes mellitus (Tos et al.,1998).The medication is commonly held either in a capsule for manual loading or a proprietary form from inside the inhaler. Once loaded or actuated, the operator puts the mouthpiece of the inhaler into their mouth and takes a deep inhalation, holding their breath for 5-10 seconds. There is a various device. The dose that can be delivered is commonly less than a few tens of milligrams in a single breath since larger powder doses may lead to provocation of cough (Haruta et al., 2012).

Insufflators

Insufflators are the devices to deliver the drug molecule for inhalation; it can be produced by using a straw or tube which contains the drug molecules and occasionally it contains syringe also. The achieved particle size of these systems is usually increased compared to the particle size of the powder particles due to insufficient disaggregation of the particles and conclusion in a high coefficient of variation for initial deposition areas. A various insufflator systems work with pre-dosed powder doses in capsules.

Pressurized Metered-Dose inhale (PMDI)

A metered-dose inhaler (MDI) is a device that delivers an exact number of drugs to the lungs, in the form of a short burst of aerosolized drug that is inhaled by the patient. It is generally

used delivery system for treating asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and other respiratory diseases. The drug delivery in a metered dose inhaler is commonly a bronchodilator, corticosteroid or a combination of both for the treatment of asthma and COPD. Like Other medications less used but also administered by MDI are mast cell stabilizers, such as (cromoglicate or nedocromil). The many advantages of MDIs are their portability and small size, availability over a wide do-sage range per actuation, dose consistency, dose accuracy, protection of the contents and that they are quickly ready for use. To use the inhaler the patient presses down on the top of the canister, with their thumb supporting the lower portion of the actuator. The propellant gives the force to generate the aerosol cloud and is also the medium in which the active component must be suspended or dissolved. Propellants in MDIs typically make up more than 99 % of the delivered dose. Actuation of the device releases a single metered dose of the formulation which contains the drug either dissolved or suspended in the propellant. Breakup of the volatile propellant into droplets, followed by rapid evaporation of these droplets, outcomes in the generation of an aerosol consisting of micrometre-sized medication particles that are then inhaled(Djupestrand, 2012).

Breath-powered Bi-Directional technology

The Breath-powered Bi-Directional technology is a novel concept for delivering the drug molecule to direct nose to brain administration. It is most advanced novel approach for delivering the powder and liquid formulation to intranasal administration. The “breath-powered” mechanism permits release of liquid or powder particles into an air stream that enters one nostril, passes totally around the nasal septum, and exits through the opposite nostril, following a Bi-Directional flow path. Actuation of drug release in devices holding this approach has been described using manual triggering as well as mechanisms automatically triggered by flow and/or pressure. By optimizing design parameters, such as the nosepiece shape, the flow rate, the particle size profile, and release angle, it is possible to optimize delivery to target sites beyond the nasal valve, avoid lung deposition, and to assure that particles are deeply deposited without exiting the contralateral nostril. The Bi-Directional devices currently in phase three clinical trials are a multi-dose liquid device integrating a standard spray pump and a capsule-based powder multi-use device with disposable drug chamber and nosepiece, but other configurations are possible. Essentially, the Bi-Directional delivery concept can be adapted to a various of dispersion technologies for both liquids and powders(Djupestrand, 2012).

Liquid formulation devices

Liquid nasal devices are delivering the aqueous or watery solutions to nasal cavity. The suspension and emulsions are also transported to nasal cavity for intranasal delivery. Liquid nasal formulations are studied convenient particularly for topical manifestation where humidification counteracts the dryness and crusting often accompanying chronic nasal diseases.

Figure 7. Nasal delivery devices: Insufflators (A), Dry powder inhaler (B), Pressurized Metered Dose Inhale (C), Breath-powered Bi-Directional technology (D), Sprays and Solution (E), Instillation and rhinyle catheter (F), Compressed air nebulizers (G), Squeezed bottle (H), Metered-dose pump sprays (I), Single and duo dose spray devices (J), ViaNase atomizer (K)

Drops delivered with pipette

Drops and vapour delivery are possibly the oldest dosage forms of nasal delivery. Dripping breast milk has been used to treatment of nasal congestion in infants, vapours of menthol or similar substances were used to watch people that have fainted, and both drops and vapours still exist on the market. Drops were basically administered by sucking liquid into a glass dropper, inserting the dropper into the nostril with an extended neck before squeezing the rubber top to emit the drops. For multi-use purposes, drops have to a large extent been replaced by metered-dose spray pumps, but inexpensive single-dose pipettes produced by “blow-fill-seal” technique are still common for OTC products like decongestants and saline. In addition, due to inadequate clinical efficacy of spray pumps in patients with nasal polyps, a nasal drop formulation of fluticasone in single-dose pipettes was introduced in the EU for the treatment of nasal polyps. The reason for this form of delivery is to improve drug deposition to the middle meatus where the polyps emerge. However, although drops work well for some, their popularity is limited by the need for head-down body positions and/or extreme neck extension required for the desired gravity driven deposition of drops. Compliance is generally poor as patients with rhinosinusitis often experience increased headache and discomfort in head-down positions (Djupesland, 2012).

Instillation and Rhinyle catheter

World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research Catheters are used to deliver the drop in appropriate region of nasal cavity. The formulation in the tube and kept tube one end was positioned in the nose, and the solution was approached into the nasal cavity by blowing

through the other end by mouth. Dosing of catheters is determined by the filling prior to administration and accuracy of the system and this system is applicable for experimental studies only (Djupesland, 2012).

Compressed air nebulizers

Nebulizers are the nasal administration devices in which the drug loaded formulation in the gaseous state deliver to the lungs. It is a compressed air filling devices for delivering the drug formulation to nasal cavity. This device is more applicable for targeting the drug formulation to respiratory tract to give rapid on-set of action and reduces the toxic effects. This device is not applicable for drug delivering into systemic pathways (Djupesland, 2012).

Metered-dose pump sprays

Most of the pharmaceutical nasal formulation such as suspension, emulsion, solution are directly delivered to intranasal pathway by using metered dose pump sprays. It is used for treatment of nasal hypersensitivity and other nasal disorders. It is based on hand operated pump mechanism. It is most important to give local effect such as topical decongestants, corticosteroids, antihistamines. This container can be containing the pump, valve and the actuator. Dose of metered dose pump sprays depends upon the viscosity and surface tension of that formulations (Djupesland, 2012).

Squeezed bottle

Squeeze bottles is used to deliver some over the counter (OTC) products like topical decongestants. They are smooth plastic bottles with simple jet outlet by pressing the bottle air passes in inside the container is pressed out of the small nozzle, having the optimum volume. After minimizing the pressure, the air again passes to inside the bottles. The dose and particle size vary with the force applied, and when the pressure is released, nasal secretion and microorganisms may be sucked into the bottle. Squeeze bottles are not recommended for children. (Djupesland, 2012).

Single and Duo dose spray devices

Single dose devices are administered single dose of drug formulation to the intranasal pathway and duo dose device administered more than one dose of different or same drug formulation intranasal cavity. A simple variant of a single-dose spray device (MAD) is offered by LMA (LMA, Salt Lake City, UT, USA). A nosepiece with a spray tip is fitted to a standard syringe. The liquid formulation to be delivered is first drawn into the syringe and then the spray tip is fitted onto the syringe. This Drug Delivery and Transl. Res. device has been used in academic studies to deliver, for example, a topical steroid in patients with chronic rhinosinusitis and in a vaccine study (Djupesland, 2012).

Nasal pressurized metered dose inhalers

Most drugs designed for local nasal action are delivered by spray pumps, but some have also been delivered as nasal aerosols produced by pMDIs. Following the ban on ozone depleting chlorofluorocarbon (CFC) propellants, the number of pMDI products for both pulmonary and nasal delivery diminished rapidly, and they were removed from the US market in 2003. The use of the old CFC pMDIs for nasal products was limited due to complaints of nasal irritation

and dryness. The particles from a pMDI are released at a high speed and the expansion of a compressed gas, which causes an uncomfortable “cold Freon effect”.

The particles emitted from the traditional pMDIs had a particle velocity much higher than a spray pump (5,200 vs. 1,500 cm/s at a distance 1–2 cm from the actuator tip). The issues related to the high particle speed and “cold Freon effect” have been reduced with the recently introduced hydrofluoroalkane (HFA)-based pMDI for nasal use offering lower particle speeds. Recently, the first nasal pMDI using HFA as propellant to deliver the first-generation topical steroid beclomethasone dipropionate (BDP) was approved for allergic rhinitis in the USA. Like spray pumps, nasal pMDIs produce a localized deposition on the anterior non-ciliated epithelium of the nasal vestibule and in the anterior parts of the narrow nasal valve, but due to quick evaporation of the spray delivered with a pMDI, noticeable “drip-out” may be less of an issue(Djupešland, 2012).

Via Nase atomizer

A handheld battery-driven atomizer intended for nasal drug delivery has been introduced (Via Nase by Kurve Technology Inc., Lynnwood, WA, USA). This device atomizes liquids by producing a vortical flow on the droplets as they exit the device. The induced vortical flow characteristics can be altered in circular velocity and direction to achieve different droplet trajectories. As discussed above, it is not clear that vortex flow is desirable for penetration past the nasal valve; however, it has been suggested that this technology is capable of targeting the sinuses, and some gamma-deposition images suggesting delivery to the sinuses have been published(Djupešland, 2012).

However, no information related to impact of prior surgery or numerical quantification of nasal or sinus deposition verifying the claimed improved deposition to the upper parts of the nose has been published. The Via Nase device has been used to deliver nasal insulin in patients with early Alzheimer’s disease (AD), and clinical benefit has been demonstrated. In these studies, delivery of insulin was performed over a 2 min period by nasal inhalation. However, when insulin is delivered with this device, lung deposition is likely to occur, and some concerns related to airway irritation and reduction in pulmonary function have been raised in relation to long-term exposure to inhaled insulin when Exubera was marketed for a short period as a treatment for diabetes. This example highlights the issue of unintended lung delivery, one important potential clinical problem associated with using nebulizers and atomizers producing respirable particles for nasal drug delivery(Djupešland, 2012).

Marketed product under nasal drug delivery system

The marketed product under nasal drug delivery system for treatment of various disorders is reported.

Brain disorders	Drug name	Product name	Nasal delivery	Manufacturer
Migraine	Dihydroergotamine	Migranal	Nasal spray	Novartis Pharma
Migraine	Zolmitriptan	AscoTop/ Zomig	Nasal spray	AstraZeneca
Migraine and pain	Butorphanol tartarate	Stadol NS	Nasal spray	Bristol-Myers Squibb
Cranial diabetes insipidus	Desmopressin	DDAVP	Nasal spray	Ferring Pharmaceuticals Ltd
Lactation induction	Oxytocin	Syntocinon	Nasal spray	Novartis Pharma

CONCLUSION

Nose to brain drug delivery bypasses the BBB to target CNS, reducing systemic exposure of drug, thereby reducing the systemic side effects. It is an interested option of drug delivery due to its non-invasiveness. These concluded findings may be crucial in developing therapeutically efficacious product in the management of chronic brain diseases otherwise difficult to treat brain tumours, epilepsy, migraine and neurodegenerative diseases. Despite the enormous progress, still there is a need for a device for selective delivery of the product at the olfactory region in the nasal cavity. The drug delivery targeting nose to brain it should be evaluated for their safety and risk-benefit ratio for the patients. It is most important point that needs to be noticed that any delivery systems developed should have no significant impact, short or long term, on the functions of the brain. Colloidal carriers offer endless opportunities in the field of drug delivery. It should be completely detailed so that it would provide useful information and progress in this line of novel research.

REFERENCES

1. Mittal, D., Ali, A., Shadab, M D., Baboota, S., Sahni, J. K. & Ali, J. Insights into Direct Nose to Brain Delivery: Current Status and Future Perspective. *Drug Deliv*, Early Online, 2013; 1-12.
2. Ugwoke, M.I., Agu, R.U., Verbeke, N., Kinget, R. Nasal Mucoadhesive Drug Delivery: Background, Applications, Trends and Future Perspectives. *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev*, 2005; 57: 1640-1665.
3. Garcia, G. E., Andrieux, K., Gilb, S., Couvreur, P. Colloidal Carriers and Blood–Brain Barrier (Bbb) Translocation: A Way to Deliver Drugs to The Brain? *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*, 2005; 298: 274-292.

4. Kumar, M., Mishra, A., Babbar, A. K., Mishra, A. K., Mishra, P., Pathak, K. Intranasal Nanoemulsion Based Brain Targeting Drug Delivery System of Risperidone. *Int J Pharm*, 2008; 358: 285-291.
5. Telling, O. V., Arik, Y. B., De Gooijer, M. C., Wesseling, P., Wurdinger, T., De Vries, H. E. Overcoming the Blood–Brain Tumor Barrier for Effective Glioblastoma Treatment. *Drug Resistance Updates*, 2015; 1-12.
6. Kamble, M. S., Bhalerao, K.K., Bhosale, A. V. & Chaudhari, P. D. A Review on Nose To-Brain Drug Delivery. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Chemical Sciences*, 2013; 2(1): 516-525.
7. Fernandes, C., Soni, U., Patravale, V. Nano-Interventions for Neurodegenerative Disorders. *Pharmacological Research*, 2010; 62: 166-178.
8. Swartling, F. J. Identifying Candidate Genes Involved In Brain Tumor Formation. *Upsala J Med Sci*, 2016; 113(1): 1-37.
9. Hussain, A. A. Intranasal Drug Delivery. *Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews*, 1998; 29: 39-49.
10. Putheti, R. R., Patil, M. C. & Obire, O. Nasal Drug Delivery in Pharmaceutical and Biotechnology: Present and Future. *E-Journal of Science & Technology (E-Jst)*, 2009; (3): 1-21.
11. Dey, S., Mahanti, B., Mazumder, B., Malgope, A. & Dasgupta, S. Nasal Drug Delivery: An Approach of Drug Delivery Through Nasal Route. *Der Pharmacia Sinica*, 2011; 2(3): 94-106.
12. Ghori, M. U., Mahdi, M. H., Smith, A. M., Conway, B. R. Nasal Drug Delivery Systems: An Overview. *American Journal of Pharmacological Sciences*, 2015; 3(5): 110-119.
13. Rahisuddin, Sharma, P.K., Garg, G. & Salim, M. Review on Nasal Drug Delivery System with Recent Advancemnt. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci*, 2011; 3(2): 6-11.
14. Stieber, D., Siti, A., Rahim, A. & Niclou, S. P. Novel Ways to Target Brain Tumour Metabolism. *Expert Opin. Ther. Targets*, 2011; 15(10): 1227-1239.
15. Parvathi, M. Intranasal Drug Delivery to Brain: An Overview. *Ijrpc*, 2012; 2(3): 889-895.
16. Arora, P., Sharma, S. & Garg, S. Permeability Issues in Nasal Drug Delivery. *Drug Discovery Today (Ddt)*, 2002; 7(18): 967-975.
17. Pagar, S., Dattatraya, M. S., Bhanudas, S. R. A Review on Intranasal Drug Delivery System. *Journal of Advanced Pharmacy Education & Research*, 2013; 3(4): 333-346.
18. Kumar, P. T., Sirisha, B. P., Narayana, R. K. & Reddy, G. N. Nasal Drug Delivery: A Potential Route for Brain Targeting. *The Pharma Innovation-Journal*, 2013; 2(1): 77-85.
19. Illum, L. Nasal Drug Delivery-Possibilities, Problems and Solutions. *Journal of Controlled Release*, 2003; 87: 187-198.

20. Misra, A. & Kher, G. Drug Delivery Systems from Nose to Brain. *Current Pharmaceutical Biotechnology*, 2012; 13: 2355-2379.
21. Falcao, A., Pires, A., Fortuna, A. & Alves, G. Intranasal Drug Delivery: How, Why and What For. *J Pharm Pharmaceut Sci (Www.Cspscanada. Org)*, 2009; 12(3): 288-311.
22. Bahadur, S. & Pathak, K. Physicochemical and Physiological Considerations for Efficient Nose-To-Brain Targeting. *Expert Opin. Drug Deliv*, 2012; 9(1): 19-31.
23. Jadhav, K. R., Gambhire, M. N., Shaikh, I. M., Kadam, V. J. & Pisal, S. S. Nasal Drug Delivery System-Factors Affecting and Applications. *Current Drug Therapy*, 2007; 2(1): 27-38.
24. Soeda, A., Inagaki, A., Oka, N., Ikegame, Y., Aoki, H., Yoshimura, Si, Nakashima, S., Kunisada, T. & Iwama, T. Epidermal Growth Factor Plays a Crucial Role In Mitogenic Regulation Of Human Brain Tumor Stem Cells. *The Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 2008; 283(16): 10958-10966.
25. Basu, S. & Bandopadhyay, A.K. Nasal Drug Delivery: An Overview. *Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Tech*, 2010; 1: 1-20.
26. Prajapati, J., Patel, K., Agrawal, Y.K. Targeted Drug Delivery for Central Nervous System: A Review. *Int. J. Pharm. Pharm. Sci*, 2012; 3: 32-38.
27. Kublik, H, Vidgren, Mt. Nasal Delivery System and Their Effects on Deposition and Absorption. *Advance Drug Delivery Review*, 1998; 29: 157-177.
28. Nagpal, K., Singh, S.K. & Mishra, D. N. Drug Targeting to Brain: A Systematic Approach to Study the Factors, Parameters and Approaches for Prediction of Permeability of Drugs Across Bbb. *Expert Opin. Drug Deliv. [Early Online]*, 2013; 1-29.
29. Thorne, R.G, Pronk, G.J, Padmanabhan, V. Frey Wh. Delivery of Insulin-Like Growth Factor-I To the Rat Brain and Spinal Cord Along Olfactory and Trigeminal Pathways Following Intranasal Administration. *Neuroscience*, 2004; 127: 481-96.
30. Schaefer, M.L., Bottger, B., Silver, W.L., Finger, T.E. Trigeminal Collaterals in The Nasal Epithelium and Olfactory Bulb: A Potential Route for Direct Modulation of Olfactory Information by Trigeminal Stimuli. *J. Comp. Neurol*, 2002; 444(3): 221-226.
31. Mark, R., & Gilbert, Md. Designing Clinical Trials for Brain Tumors: The Next Generation. *Current Oncology Report*, 2007; 9: 49-54.
32. Soni, V., Chorasias, Mk., Gupta, Y., Jain, A., Kohli, Dv. & Jain Sk. Novel Approaches for Drug Delivery to The Brain. *Indian J. Pharm. Sci*, 2004; 66: 711- 720.
33. Jain, R., Nabar, S., Dandekar, P., Patravale, V. Micellar Nanocarriers: Potential Nose-To Brain Delivery of Zolmitriptan as Novel Migraine Therapy. *Pharm Res*, 2010; 4: 655-64.
34. Lalani, J., Baradia, D., Lalani, R. & Misra, A. Brain Targeted Intranasal Delivery of Tramadol: Comparative Study of Microemulsion and Nanoemulsion. *Pharm Dev Technol, Early Online*, 2014; 1-10.

35. Kulkarni, K., Bhambere, T., Chaudhary, G., Talele, S., Moghal, R. Brain Targetting Through Intranasal Route. *Int.J.Pharmtech Res*, 2013; 5(4): 1441-1450.
36. Alagusundaram, M., Chengaiah, B., Gnanaprakash, K., Ramkanth, S., Chetty, C. M., Dhachinamoorthi, D. Nasal Drug Delivery System - An Overview. *Int. J. Res. Pharm. Sci*, 2010; 1(4): 454-465.
37. Wu, H., Hu, K. & Jiang, X. From Nose to Brain: Understanding Transport Capacity and Transport Rate of Drugs. *Expert Opin. Drug Deliv*, 2008; 5(10): 1159-1168.
38. Nasare, L., Niranjane, K., Nagdevte, A., Mohril, S. Nasal Drug Delivery System: An Emerging Approach for Brain Targeting. *Wjpps*, 2014; 3(4): 539-553.
39. Paul, E. M., Nigavekar, S. S., Bielinska, A. U., Mank, N., Shetty, A. M., Suman, J., Knowlton, J., Myc, A., Rook, T & Baker, J. R., Characterization of Stability and Nasal Delivery Systems for Immunization with Nanoemulsion-Based Vaccines. *Journal of Aerosol Medicine and Pulmonary Drug Delivery*, 2010; 23(2): 77-89.
40. Wong, H. L., Wu, X. Y., Bendayan, R. Nanotechnological Advances for the Delivery of Cns Therapeutics. *Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews*, 2012; 64: 686-700.
41. Mourya, V. K. & Inamdar, N. N. Chitosan-Modifications and Applications: Opportunities Galore. *Reac. Func. Poly*, 2008; 68: 1013-1051.
42. Wang, Y.Y., Lai, S.K., Suk, J.S., Pace, A., Cone, R., Hanes, J. b. Addressing The Peg Mucoadhesivity Paradox To Engineer Nanoparticles That “Slip”. Through The Human Mucus Barrier. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl*, 2008; 47: 9726-9729.
43. Gao, X.L., Tao, W.X., Lu, W., Zhang, Q.Z., Zhang, Y., Jiang, X.G., Fu, S.K. Lectin Conjugated Peg-Pla Nanoparticles: Preparation and Brain Delivery After Intranasal Administration. *Biomaterials*, 2006; 27: 3482-3490.
44. Casettari, L, Villasaliu, D, Castagnino, E, Et Al. Pegylated Chitosan Derivatives: Synthesis, Characterizations and Pharmaceutical Applications. *Prog Polym Sci*, 2010; 5: 659-85.
45. Lin, Y. M., Wu, J.Y., Chen, Y. C., Su, Y.D., Ke, W.T., Ho, H.O., Sheu, M.T. In Situ Formation of Nanocrystals from A Self-Microemulsifying Drug Delivery System to Enhance Oral Bioavailability of Fenofibrate. *International Journal of Nanomedicine*, 2011; 6: 2445-2457.
46. Guo, F., Zhong, H., He, J., Xie, B., Liu, F., Xu, H., Liu, M., & Xu, C. Self Microemulsifying Drug Delivery System for Improved Oral Bioavailability of Dipyridamole: Preparation and Evaluation, *Arch Pharm Res*, 2011; 34 (7): 1113-1123.
47. Bhosale, R. R., Osmani, R. A., Ghodake, P. P., Shaikh, S. M., Chavan, S. R. Nanoemulsion: A Review on Novel Profusion in Advanced Drug Delivery. *Indian J.Pharm.Biol.Res*, 2014; 2(1): 122-127.
48. Jaiswal, M., Dudhe, R., Sharma, P. K. Nanoemulsion: An Advanced Mode of Drug Delivery System. *3 Biotech Springer*, 2015; 3(5): 123-127.

49. Patel, Z. S., Shah, R., Shah, D. N., Nanoemulsion: An Innovative Approach for Topical Delivery. *Pharma Science Monitor*, 2016; 7(2): 21-36.
50. Dinger, A., Blum, R.P., Niehus, H., Müller, R.H., Gohla, S. Solid Lipid Nanoparticles (SInTM/LipopearlTM)-A Pharmaceutical and Cosmetic Carrier for The Application of Vitamin E In Dermal Products. *J Microencapsul*, 1999; 16(6): 751-767.
51. Gasco, M.R. Method for Producing Solid Lipid Nanospheres with Warm Microemulsions. *Pharm Tech Eur*, 1997; 9: 52-58.
52. Ekambaram, P., Hassan, A., Sathali, A. Solid Lipid Nanoparticles: A Review. *Sci Revs Chem Commun*, 2012; 2(1): 80-102.
53. Mistry, A., Stolnik, S., Illum, L. Nanoparticles for Direct Nose-To Brain Delivery of Drugs. *Int. J. Pharm.*, 2009; 379(1): 146-57.
54. Seju, U., Kumar, A., Sawant, K.K. Development and Evaluation of Olanzapine-Loaded Plga Nanoparticles for Nose-To-Brain Delivery: In Vitro and In Vivo Studies. *Acta Biomaterialia*, 2011; 7: 4169-4176.
55. Kwon, G.S. & Okano, T. Polymeric Micelles as New Drug Carriers. *Adv. Drug Del. Rev*, 1996; 21:107-116.
56. Nishiyama, N. & Kataoka, K. Current State, Achievements, and Future Prospects of Polymeric Micelles as Nanocarriers for Drug and Gene Delivery. *Pharmacol. Ther*, 2006; 112: 630- 648.
57. Tengamnuay, P., Mitra, A.K. Bile Salt-Fatty Acid Mixed Micelles as Nasal Absorption Promoters of Peptides. I. Effects of Ionic Strength, Adjuvant Composition, and Lipid Structure on The Nasal Absorption of [D-Arg²] Kyotorphin. *Pharm. Res*, 1990; 7(2): 127-33.
58. Goyal, P., Goyal, K., Kumar, S.G.V., Singh, A., Katare, O.P., Mishra, D.N. Liposomal Drug Delivery Systems-Clinical Applications. *Acta Pharm*, 2005; 55: 1-25.
59. Shim, C.K., Ahn, B.N., Kim, S.K. Preparation and Evaluation of Proliposomes Containing Propranolol Hydrochloride. *J Microencapsul*, 1995; 12(4): 363-75.
60. Frey, W.H. Method for Administering Fibroblast Growth Factor to The Brain. *Us Patent*, 2010; 6342478, 6342478/Method-For-Administering-Fibroblast-Growthfactor-To-The Brain (Accessed On 8th March 2010).
61. Vyas, S.P., Goswami, S.K., Singh, R. Liposomes Based Nasal Delivery System of Nifedipine: Development and Characterization. *Int. J. Pharm*, 1995; 118(1): 23-30.
62. Khan, S., Patil K., Bobade N., Et Al. Formulation of Intranasal Mucoadhesive Temperature-Mediated in Situ Gel Containing Ropinirole and Evaluation of Brain Targeting Efficiency in Rats. *J Drug Target*, 2010; 3: 223-234.
63. Illum, L., Farraj, N.F., Davis, S.S. Chitosan as A Novel Nasal Delivery System for Peptide Drugs. *Pharm. Res.*, 1994; 11(8): 1186-1189.
64. Patel, N.R., Patel, D.A., Bharadia, P.D, Pandya, V., Modi, V. Microsphere as A Novel Drug Deliver, *Int J Of Pharm & Life Sci*, 2011; 2(8): 992-997.

65. Stahl, K., Claesson, M., Lilliehorn, P., Linden, H., Backstrom, K. The Effect of Process Variables on The Degradation and Physical Properties of Spray Dried Insulin Intended For Inhalation, *Int J Pharm.*, 2002; 233: 227-237.
66. Rathananand, M., Kumar, D.S., Shirwaikar, A., Kumar, R., Kumar, D.S., Prasad, R.S. Preparation of Mucoadhesive Microspheres for Nasal Delivery by Spray Drying, *Indian J Pharm Sci.*, 2007; 69: 651-657.
67. Wolfe T. Intranasal Fentanyl for Acute Pain: Techniques to Enhance Efficacy. *Ann. Emerg. Med.*, 2007; 49(5): 721-722.
68. Huge, V., Lauchart, M., Magerl, W., Schelling, G., Beyer, A., Thieme, D., Azad, S. C. Effects of Low-Dose Intranasal (S)-Ketamine in Patients with Neuropathic Pain. *Eur. J. Pain*, 2010; 14(4): 387-394.
69. Hanson, L.R. & Frey Ii, W.H. Strategies for Intranasal Delivery of Therapeutics for the Prevention and Treatment of Neuro Aids. *J. Neuroimmune Pharm*, 2007; 2(1): 81-86.
70. Kublik, H. & Vidgren, Mt. Nasal Delivery Systems and Their Effect on Deposition and Absorption. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev*, 1998; 29: 157-77.
71. Tos, M., Svendstrup, F., Arndal, H., Et Al. Efficacy of An Aqueous and A Powder Formulation of Nasal Budesonide Compared in Patients with Nasal Polyps. *Am J Rhinol*, 1998; 12: 183-189.
72. Haruta, S. & Tsutsui, T. Meeting the Needs for Nasal Delivery Devices for Powder Formulations. *Drug Dev Deliv*, 2012; 12(5): 22-27.
73. Huang, J., Garmise, R. J., Crowder, T. M., Mara, K., Hwanga, C. R., Hickey, A. J., Mikszta, J. A., Sullivan, V. J. A Novel Dry Powder Influenza Vaccine and Intranasal Delivery Technology: Induction of Systemic and Mucosal Immune Responses in Rats. *Vaccine*, 2004; 23: 794-801.
74. Djupesland, P. G, Skretting, A., Windern, M., Holand, T. Breath Actuated Device Improves Delivery to Target Sites Beyond the Nasal Valve. *Laryngoscope*, 2006; 116: 466-472.
75. Skretting, A., Djupesland, P. G. A New Method for Scintigraphic Quantification of Deposition and Clearance in Anatomical Regions of The Human Nose. *Nucl Med Comm*, 2009; 30(8): 629-638.
76. Hansen, F., Djupesland, P. G, Fokkens, W. J. Effective Treatment of Chronic Rhinosinusitis with Fluticasone Delivered by A Novel Device: A Randomized Placebo Controlled Pilot Study. *Rhinology*, 2010; 48: 292-299.
77. Reiber, H., Felgenhauer, K. Protein Transfer at The Blood Cerebrospinal Fluid Barrier and The Quantitation of The Humoral Immune Response Within the Central Nervous System. *Clin Chim Acta*, 1987; 163: 319-328.
78. Renteria, S. S., Clemens, C. C., Croyle, M. A. Development of A Nasal Adenovirus Based Vaccine: Effect of Concentration and Formulation on Adenovirus Stability and Infectious Titer During Actuation from Two Delivery Devices. *Vaccine*, 2010; 28: 2137-2148.

79. Möller, W., Saba, G. K., Häussinger, K., Becker, S., Keller, M., Schuschnig, U. Nasally Inhaled Pulsating Aerosols: Lung, Sinus and Nose Deposition. *Rhinology*, 2011; 49: 286-291.
80. Vecellio, L., De Gersem, R., Le Guellec, S., Et Al. Deposition of Aerosols Delivered by Nasal Route with Jet and Mesh Nebulizers. *Int J Pharm*, 2011; 407: 87-94.
81. Hoekman, J. D. & Ho, R. J. Y. Enhanced Analgesic Responses After Preferential Delivery of Morphine and Fentanyl to The Olfactory Epithelium in Rats. *AnesthAnalg*, 2011; 113: 641-651.
82. Soane, R. J., Frier, M, Perkins, A. C., Jones, N. S., Davis, S. S., Illum, L. Evaluation of The Clearance Characteristics of Bioadhesive Systems in Humans. *Int J Pharma.*, 1999; 178: 55-65.
83. Frenkel, D., Maron, R., Burt, D., Weiner, H. L. Compositions and Methods for Treating Neurological Disorders, 2006; Us0229233a1.
84. Choi Ym. & Kim Kh. Transnasal Microemulsions Containing Diazepam, 2005; Us0002987a1.
85. Choi Ym. & Kim Kh. Transnasal Microemulsions Containing Diazepam, 2004; Wo04110403a1. 86. Misra A. & Vyas Tk. Drugs Loaded Nasoadhesive Microemulsions for Brain Targeted Brisk Delivery in Acute Epilepsy, 2005; 1061: 2004. 87. Misra A. & Vyas Tk. Sedatives Loaded Intranasal Nasoadhesive Microemulsions for Brain Targeted Delivery in Insomnia, 2005; 1124: 2004.
88. Misra A. & Vyas Tk. Drugs Loaded Intranasal Nasoadhesive Microemulsions for Brain Targeted Delivery in Migraine, 2005; 1125: 2004.
89. Wermeling Dp. System and Method for Intranasal Administration of Lorazepam, 2003; Us6610271b2.
90. Wermeling Dp. System and Method for Intranasal Administration of Lorazepam, 2001; Us0055571a1.
91. Castile Jd, Cheng Yh, Jenkins Pg, Et Al. Intranasal Compositions, 2007; Us0140981a1.
92. Meyerson Lr, Went Gt, Fultz Tj. Methods And Compositions for The Treatment of Cns Related Conditions, 2005; Us0245617a1.
93. Frey Whli. Method for Administering Insulin to the Brain, 2001. Us6313093b1. 94. Frey Whli. Method for Administering Neurological Agents to the Brain, 2001; Us6180603b1.
95. Frey Whli. Method for Administering Neurological Agents to the Brain, 1997; Us5624898.
96. Frey Whli, Thorne Rg. Method For Administering Agents to the Central Nervous System, 2003; Us0072793a1.
97. Frey Whli. Method for Administering Brain-Derived Neurotropic Factor to The Brain, 2003; Us0215398a1.

98. Frey Whli, Danielyan L, Christoph H. Methods, Pharmaceutical Compositions and Articles of Manufacture for Administering Therapeutic Cells to The Animal Central Nervous System, 2012; Us8283160b2.
99. Hallschmid, M., Benedict, C., Schultes, B., Fehm, H.L., Born, J., Kern, W. Intranasal Insulin Reduces Body Fat in Men but Not in Women. *Diabetes*, 2004; 53(11): 3024-3029.
100. Ross, T.M., Martinez, P.M., Renner, J.C., Thorne, R.G., Hanson, L.R., Frey li, W.H. Intranasal Administration of Interferon Beta Bypasses the Blood-Brain Barrier to Target the Central Nervous System and Cervical Lymph Nodes: A Non-Invasive Treatment Strategy for Multiple Sclerosis. *J. Neuroimmunol*, 2004; 151(1-2): 66-77.